

DECONSTRUCTING WOMEN'S REPRESENTATION IN PHILIPPINE TV ADVERTISEMENTS: A BARTHESIAN SEMIOLOGICAL APPROACH ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the image projected to women in Philippine TV advertisements. It sought to identify the prevailing traditional gender roles assigned to women "Y Company" a multinational company of household products in the Philippines, while also examining the emergence of new identities and representations. Guided by Roland Barthes' Semiotics, this qualitative study employed gathered 15 unduplicated advertisements in the year 2023-2024 from the Philippines' top network. Images from these advertisements were then collected and analyzed to explore the underlying messages at both denotative and connotative levels of significance. The study revealed that the advertisements predominantly depicted women as wives and homemakers responsible for household chores. This continues traditional gender roles and emphasizes societal expectations that confine women to stereotypical roles within the domestic sphere. Although some emerging roles were observed, women were still largely portrayed in domestic capacities. While the company's advertisements have witnessed the emergence of new roles, it is evident that a significant portion of their content still reinforces traditional gender stereotypes. To enhance these portrayals opposing the limited portrayals of women in household tasks, the company may continue to make progress towards a more inclusive and empowering depiction of women in their advertisements which celebrates diversity, strength, and achievements of women in all aspects of life. Further, individuals who regularly engage with media may become more attuned to the representations of women. By questioning these representations, one may begin to recognize the underlying biases and stereotypes that may be perpetuated by certain advertisements.

Keywords: *advertisements; denotative; connotative; women; semiotics*

INTRODUCTION

TV advertisements are one of the oldest ways of marketing and remain popular due to their ability to reach a wide audience, facilitating brand influence and awareness. In addition, TV advertisements typically consist of 30-second segments and utilize various creative elements such as music, sound effects, visual effects, and either a voiceover or on-screen text to engage viewers (Cunningham, 2023). Over time, advertisements have evolved beyond product promotion to communicate diverse viewpoints, values, social beliefs, conservative ideologies, and at times, even sexual content and nudity on television (Lal, 2022).

For instance, women in TV advertisements have often been depicted in traditional and domestic roles. These roles originated in the 1950s and 1960s, portraying women primarily in kitchen and family care settings. In the 1970s and 1980s, there was a shift towards portraying women as more independent and in diverse roles. However, this change was short-lived, and women continued to be portrayed in traditional or decorative roles from the 1990s into the 21st century (Urlage, 2021). As a result of these depictions, gender stereotyping has become a significant concern due to the repeated portrayal of women in conventional roles in television advertisements (Eisend, 2019).

In Philippine TV advertisements, women were also frequently depicted. According to the study by Embate and Mercado (2019), which examined 227 female characters shown in Philippine primetime TV advertisements, 42% of them played a family role, while 29% played a decorative role. Only 5% were represented in a working role, while 3% were showcased in a provider role. Furthermore, 26% of the advertisements showing women were for personal care and beauty products; 18% were for food products; and 17% were for non-alcoholic beverages. Meanwhile, women were more featured in household cleaning products (12%) than drugs or medicine (9%).

Numerous studies on the representation of women in advertising across various countries, such as the United States (Havenhill, 2022), Bangladesh (Mim & Tabassum, 2021), Nigeria (Ojomo & Adekusibe, 2020), India (Kakade & Javalkar, 2020), and Turkey (Yarimoglu, 2022), have revealed common portrayals. These portrayals often depict women in traditional roles as homemakers and housewives, responsible for domestic duties. Additionally, some studies have identified instances where women are depicted as sexual objects (Iram et al., 2023; Sharma & Bumb, 2021). Matthes and Prieler (2016) also uncovered gender stereotypes in TV advertising on a global scale through their analysis of 1,755 advertisements spanning 13 countries.

Furthermore, Faull (2023) uncovered a significant increase in the depiction of women in domestic or family environments, constituting 66% of the 10,000 advertisements analyzed in 2022, marking a notable surge from the previous year's 32%. Conversely, the portrayal of women in professional settings saw a decrease, dropping

from 16% in 2021 to a mere 7% in 2022. In essence, the research indicates a shift towards highlighting women in domestic roles while diminishing their representation in professional contexts. In addition, negative or stereotypical portrayals of women were found to adversely impact consumers' inclination to purchase the advertised products (Sharma & Bumb, 2021).

Multiple studies mentioned above have highlighted the prevalent portrayal of women in TV advertisements indicating that women are often depicted in roles associated with motherhood and homemaking. This suggests a strong association between women and parenting as well as household responsibilities in the advertising domain. Nonetheless, the aforementioned studies did not specifically examine the portrayal of women in advertisements for household products, as their primary focus was on general advertisements. This lack of attention to specified products indicates a need for targeted research into the depiction of women in advertisements for household products.

In response to this need, the researchers conducted a qualitative study focused on scrutinizing the portrayal of women in TV advertisements by “Y Company” that specializes in household products, with the primary objective of bridging the existing gap in the representation of women. The analysis of these advertisements is intended to provide invaluable insights not only for this company but also for other advertising agencies. It is believed that these insights will aid in comprehending the depictions of women in their content, thereby identifying opportunities for enhancing the presentation of a more dynamic and diverse portrayal of women.

Research Questions

This study aimed to know the image projected to women in the TV advertisements of the “Y Company” in the country. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the traditional roles of women projected in the advertisements?
2. What are the emerging identities of women shaped by these advertisements?
3. How do these identities and roles portray women in terms of:
 - 3.1 the denotative level of significance
 - 3.2 the connotative level of significance of semiotics?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this qualitative study, the researchers employed the Barthesian Semiological Approach to examine the traditional roles and emerging identities of women depicted in the advertisements from the leading company being studied. Additionally, the study aimed to assess how these identities and roles, in terms of visual representation, convey

denotative and connotative levels of significance. This approach was chosen due to its extensive use in media studies, particularly in the analysis of various media domains such as films, video clips, and advertising (Bouzida, 2014). Furthermore, the qualitative method was deemed most suitable for this study as it sought to comprehend phenomena by exploring the meanings attributed to them (Aspers & Corte, 2019).

The present study only focused on examining the portrayal of women in TV advertisements in the Philippines. Specifically, 15 unduplicated advertisements featuring female characters aired within the year 2023-2024 by GMA Network were selected for analysis. GMA was chosen due to its consistent position as the network with the highest viewership and most accolades in the Philippines.

To analyze the corpora, the researchers viewed TV advertisements and specifically gathered household products. The data collection process was facilitated by the availability of the data on the GMA network. In addition, the study focused on the prominent brands of the “Y Company”. These brands fall within the category of household products, which was the primary focus of the research. Additionally, the study employed purposive sampling to select the corpora for analysis. To facilitate organization and identification, each advertisement was assigned a code after the selection. This code comprised the abbreviation of the television advertisement, followed by the respective advertisement number. For instance, the code “TVA-01” signified television advertisement number 1.

The analysis was then initiated subsequent to the collection of the 15 advertisements, which were organized within a Word document and appropriately labelled. Each of the corpora underwent a thorough analysis utilizing the Barthesian Semiological Approach. This involved scrutinizing the traditional and emerging roles as well as discerning the denotative and connotative levels present in the images extracted from the advertisements. As explained by Azin and Tabrizi (2015), denotation refers to the literal and objective meaning of the image, while connotation encompasses the additional ideas, emotions, and cultural values evoked by the image. Further, the researchers' comprehensive elucidation provided robust support for the classification of the data.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the traditional roles of women in the 15 collected TV advertisements of the leading multinational corporation in the country. After the researchers analyz

ed the data, there were two (2) traditional roles uncovered, namely homemaker and wife.

Table 1. Traditional Roles of Women in “Y Company” Advertisements

Roles	Description	Code	Frequency (%)
Homemaker	A homemaker is an individual who manages and maintains a household, taking care of various domestic tasks and responsibilities.	TVA-03, TVA-07, TVA-10, TVA-11	4 (36%)
Wife	A wife is a partner and companion to her spouse, typically taking charge of household management and ensuring the well-being of her child.	TVA-01, TVA-02, TVA-08, TVA-09, TVA-13, TVA-14, TVA-15	7 (64%)

Table 2 presents the emerging identities portrayed in the TV advertisements produced by the same company. Through analysis, the researchers have discerned the emergence of three distinct roles: the social media influencer, teacher, and career woman. The identification of these emerging roles presents an opportunity to enhance the portrayal of women by showcasing their multifaceted capabilities beyond traditional domestic roles, thereby contributing to a more inclusive and empowering representation in advertising content.

Table 2. Emerging Identities in “Y Company” Advertisements

Roles	Description	Code	Frequency (%)
Social Media Influencer	A social media influencer is an individual who has gained a significant following and influence on social media platforms. They are considered experts or authorities in their respective niches and have the ability to impact the opinions, behaviors, and purchasing decisions of their followers.	TVA-04	1 (20%)
Teacher	A teacher is an individual who is responsible for facilitating learning, imparting knowledge, and guiding students in their educational journey.	TVA-05, TVA-12	2 (40%)
Career woman	A career woman is a term used to describe a woman who is focused on her professional development and success.	TVA-06, TVA-09	2 (40%)

Denotative and Connotative Level of Significance

Denotative Level

The visual content featured in the advertisements from “Y Company” showcases women’s involvement in a wide spectrum of activities. In the first image, a woman was shown engaging in the act of dishwashing using the brand being advertised. The image clearly indicates that numerous dishes have been effectively cleaned using this product, as evidenced on the left and right sides of the image. Additionally, another woman is depicted in the second image involved in the activity of ironing, with baskets brimming with neatly pressed clothes in the background. Conversely, the third image depicts women actively engaged in the task of doing laundry. These women are shown raising two visibly soiled shirts. One woman is using brand X, and the other is opting for the brand being advertised. In addition, a woman is shown in the kitchen holding a pan with food and showing disappointment in the fourth image. Further, amidst this representation, there are select advertisements that go beyond these conventional roles and present women in alternative capacities, notably as career women, as exemplified in the final image. Here, a woman is depicted socializing with other women in a living room setting, adorned in an elegant purple dress.

Connotative Level

The prevalent portrayal of women primarily engaged in domestic activities in these advertisements effectively perpetuates deeply ingrained gender norms and societal presumptions. These representations subtly communicate the notion that women bear the primary responsibility for these tasks, thereby reinforcing traditional gender roles and expectations within society. However, amid this prevailing depiction, there are instances where women are showcased in roles that extend beyond the confines of traditional gender stereotypes. These depictions serve as a counterbalance, emphasizing women’s capabilities and contributions in non-traditional domains, thereby challenging conventional gender norms and presenting a more empowering and positive image of women. This portrayal not only acknowledges the diversity of women’s roles and abilities but also promotes a more inclusive and equitable representation of women in various spheres of life. Nevertheless, despite an increase in the number of women represented in the advertising industry, achieving true gender equity remains a far-reaching aspiration (Karlovitich, 2023). This underscores the ongoing need for continuous efforts to challenge and break free from traditional gender stereotypes that have long been perpetuated in advertising. Furthermore, recognizing and celebrating the multifaceted nature of women’s roles and contributions in society is pivotal in fostering a more inclusive and diverse representation of women. By amplifying depictions of women in varied roles, advertisers may play a significant role in reshaping societal perceptions and fostering an environment that embraces and values the diverse roles and capabilities of women.

DISCUSSION

In Table 1, it was evident that traditional gender roles assigned to women were prevalent. The analysis revealed that these advertisements predominantly portrayed women in two primary traditional roles: as homemakers, accounting for 36% of the portrayals, and as wives, representing 64% of the portrayals.

Homemakers

The role pertains to an individual responsible for overseeing and maintaining a household, encompassing a diverse array of domestic tasks and responsibilities. Upon scrutinizing the TV advertisements from the notable company being studied, the researchers identified that 4 out of 15 advertisements depicted women engaging in household activities, particularly laundry. Some studies have indicated that women are frequently portrayed as having fewer employment opportunities outside of the home compared to men, perpetuating the stereotype of women primarily associated with domestic responsibilities (Havenhill, 2022; Alibrahim, 2023). Furthermore, these studies have highlighted that women are often depicted in advertisements set within domestic environments, specifically endorsing products related to home cleaning, cooking, and various household tasks. Meanwhile, this role further aligns with the findings presented in an article by Enriquez (2023), which explores the prevailing perception among Filipinos regarding the role of Filipino women. The article reveals that, despite societal advancements, the perception of Filipino women primarily as homemakers persists in contemporary times. This perception encompasses the expectation that women should prioritize and take charge of household management.

Wife

This role assumes the role of efficiently managing the household and ensuring the well-being of her child. In these advertisements, the researchers noted that women are prominently featured engaging in a variety of domestic tasks, including dishwashing, ironing, cooking, and childcare. Their portrayal as the primary doers of these tasks perpetuates the notion that women bear the responsibility for maintaining and managing the household as well as caring for their children. With 7 out of 15 advertisements, being a wife is the most prevalent role given to women in the advertisements of the eminent multinational corporation. In an article by Shequal (2022), it was explained that the prevalent stereotype in advertisements is often referred to as the "model mother," which perpetuates the idea that women are primarily responsible for caregiving duties within the household, including the care of children.

Consequently, Table 1 reveals that the majority of women portrayed in the distinguished corporation assume roles primarily associated with domestic responsibilities.

In Table 2, it shows that among the fifteen (15) advertisements examined, there were three (3) emerging identities found, namely: social media influencer with 20%, teacher with 40%, and career woman with 40%. These characters not only deviate from the traditional role of the sole housewife but also showcase women's ability to participate in activities typically associated with men. As such, they represent the emergence of women who are progressively gaining independence and confidence by challenging societal norms and forging their own paths.

Social Media Influencer

A social media influencer is someone who has amassed a substantial number of followers and holds considerable sway on social media platforms. TVA-04, one of the 15 advertisements, showcased a woman in the emerging role of a social media influencer. This depiction aligns with the findings of Kordrostami and Laczniak (2021), who highlights a notable shift in the portrayal of women in advertisements, showcasing them as influential figures capable of shaping the thoughts and behaviors of others. This shift opposes traditional gender stereotypes and provides positive role models for women and girls. In addition, it has the potential to drive broader social change by challenging societal norms and promoting gender equality. By showcasing women in positions of influence, these advertisements help to create a more inclusive and empowered society where women are recognized and celebrated for their capabilities and contributions.

Teacher

A teacher plays a crucial role in guiding, instructing, and mentoring students, nurturing their intellectual growth, and overall development. Among the 15 advertisements analyzed, TVA-05 and TVA-12 depicted women in the role of teachers. The inclusion of women in this specific role coincides with the analysis conducted by Murawski (2020), where it was noted that 48% of women participants perceive a positive trend in female representation in advertising over the past five years. These findings indicate a substantial number of women who have recognized and welcomed the increasing favorability of the portrayal of women in advertising. However, the research also emphasizes that there is still progress to be made in moving away from stereotypes and promoting a more positive and empowering image of women. While the shift towards more favorable representation is apparent, there remains room for improvement in ensuring that brands consistently and genuinely depict women in an empowering, diverse, and reflective manner that resonates with the realities and aspirations of women in society.

Career-woman

A career woman is an individual who places significant emphasis on achieving success in her chosen career or profession, with her primary focus revolving around her work and the pursuit of personal and professional advancement. TVA-06 and TVA-09 presented women in the emerging role of a career woman. Despite prevalent representations that diminish the status of women, these roles correspond with the findings of Miranda (2023), indicating that women in today's era have demonstrated

adaptability and have overcome limitations imposed by societal stereotypes, often encompassing contradictory traits. They have exhibited resilience by effectively managing multiple roles, driven by their passion and determination. Miranda (2023) also highlighted that women today have achieved significant accomplishments in various fields, including entertainment and business. Additionally, the analysis by Liljedal et al. (2020) revealed that when women are portrayed in traditionally male-associated job roles, it can lead to more favorable attitudes towards advertising outcomes, such as perceptions of the advertisements and the brand being advertised.

Accordingly, the data presented in Table 2 showed a trend in the depiction of women in the advertisements from the multinational company. These advertisements feature women assuming roles that are associated with being influencers and professionals.

In denotative and connotative analysis, a substantial portion of the advertising content of the leading household goods corporation in the Philippines continues to predominantly depict women as mothers or individuals primarily focused on household chores. These depictions corroborate the study of Embate and Mercado (2019), which found that there was a higher prevalence of women being prominently featured in advertisements for household cleaning products. Moreover, this perpetuation of traditional gender roles serves to reinforce societal expectations that confine women to stereotypical roles within the domestic sphere. However, it is noteworthy to consider the absence of certain advertisements that portray women engaging in activities such as doing laundry or performing household tasks. This absence in itself can be interpreted as a progressive step, signaling a departure from the stereotypical and restrictive portrayals that confine women exclusively to domestic duties. This evolving representation hints at a potential shift in the advertising landscape, reflecting a growing awareness of the need to portray women in more diverse and multifaceted roles, beyond the confines of traditional domestic responsibilities. This shift not only challenges entrenched gender stereotypes but also reflects a broader societal acknowledgment of the multifaceted capabilities and contributions of women across various spheres of life.

Conclusion

The advertisements of “Y Company” have predominantly portrayed women in the traditional roles of homemakers and wives responsible for managing the household and childcare. These depictions often reinforce the societal expectation that women are the primary ones responsible for domestic duties, perpetuating deeply ingrained gender norms and roles. However, amidst these conventional portrayals, emerging identities have begun to surface in these advertisements, showcasing women in roles such as social media influencer, teachers, and career women. These evolving representations highlight the capacity of women to engage in activities beyond traditional caregiving duties, emphasizing their versatility, capabilities, and contributions to diverse spheres of life. Nevertheless, upon denotative and connotative analysis, it becomes evident that, despite these progressive trends, the content of these advertisements continues to support traditional gender stereotypes. While there is a growing acknowledgment of

women's involvement in non-traditional roles, the essence of being homemakers is still deeply ingrained in the narratives, implying that women possess innate skills and knowledge for those duties. In light of this, there is an opportunity for advertisers, including the company being studied, to delve into the multifaceted roles and contributions of women, thereby creating a more authentic and impactful portrayal that celebrates the rich diversity of women's experiences and capabilities. By featuring women in a broader range of roles and activities, advertisers may challenge the confined portrayals of women in domestic responsibilities, ultimately progressing towards a more empowering depiction of women in their advertisements. This shift has the potential to not only reshape societal perceptions but also contribute to fostering a more inclusive representation of women in the advertising industry and beyond.

Recommendations

The findings and implications drawn from this study are of a preliminary nature, and it is imperative to conduct further extensive research in order to establish more conclusive and definitive conclusions pertaining to the portrayal and representation of women in advertisements. Other researchers have the opportunity to utilize mixed-method studies as a means of conducting comprehensive investigations, such as studying the perceptions of women regarding their depictions in advertisements. One effective approach would involve conducting interviews with women, allowing for an in-depth exploration of their thoughts and feelings towards the portrayals and typical roles assigned to them in these advertisements. By employing this method, researchers may gain insights into the emotional and psychological impacts experienced by women when they come across these depictions or encounter the stereotypical roles assigned to them in advertisements. By conducting interviews, it allows for the exploration of individual perspectives, enabling researchers to uncover the diverse range of emotions, thoughts, and beliefs held by women within this context. Further, this investigation may provide a deeper understanding of the ways in which these portrayals influence and shape women's perceptions of themselves, their identities, and their roles within society. Moreover, this present study, along with future studies, may serve as a catalyst for change, inspiring companies to go beyond traditional gender roles and embrace a more diverse and inclusive approach to their advertisements. By taking proactive steps towards enhancing the portrayal of women, the advertising industry as a whole may play a pivotal role in promoting a more progressive and inclusive society.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers did not need to conduct an in-person interview as the focus was on analyzing the advertisements in the Philippines. Instead, the investigation centered on the broadcast advertisements of the company being studied. Furthermore, in compliance with data privacy regulations, the researchers opted not to disclose the identity of the company under study, instead referring to it as "Y Company". This approach upholds the confidentiality of the company's information while still enabling the researchers to present the study. In addition, this study underwent language editing and plagiarism checks to ensure its authenticity. Conversely, the interpretation of the findings in this study was

ensured to be free from bias or prejudice.

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